

Where Were You During the Revolution? The Construction of a New Privileged Class in Post-Asad Syria¹

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“Whoever liberates decides.”

[Man yuharrir yuqarrir.]

-Popular slogan (origin unknown)

To whom does the revolution belong? In the immediate aftermath of the fall of Bashar al-Asad, euphoric proclamations of the triumph of the Syrian people were broadcast widely by the revolution’s supporters as Syria’s new rulers aimed to unify the country and allay the concerns of those who were skeptical of their intentions. Over time, the boundaries of who could claim ownership over the victory became increasingly contested. For good reason, much of the discourse examining this phenomenon has either focused on the legitimacy of the authority wielded by actors associated with Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (HTS) or rising sectarian tensions. In relation to the slogan in the epigraph, a number of critics have noted how such sentiments can have disastrous consequences in terms of the autocratization of the regime that ultimately stabilizes and the governance that follows (Ali 2025; Al-Harithi 2025). Yet, few have dis-

cussed the implications of the battle over who deserves to shape the future of Syria on the formation of a privileged class that is tied to the new governing authorities, beyond coarse examinations of sectarian identity (Ayek 2025).

This short piece is based on preliminary research into changes in social relations in Syria during the transitional period following the end of Asad’s rule. The views expressed here are provisional and draw primarily on observations from Damascus. In writing this, I was also prompted to reflect on a future that is inherently uncertain. With those caveats in mind, I contend that the transition in Syria has produced the rise of a privileged class whose identity is rooted in their presence in Idlib prior to Asad’s fall.

No social order operates independently of its political order. The political viability of a social group can shape political competition between groups, which can ultimately affect intergroup relations (Posner 2004).² More-

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² While Posner’s focus is on political competition, he also discusses antagonistic intergroup relations.

over, just as rulers face strong incentives to limit concessions by narrowing the pool of individuals within the ruling elite (Geddes 2004), beneficiaries of the political order beyond the ruling elite may wish to limit the scope of those included in order to enjoy a greater share of the benefits. As such, the salience of various social divisions within a state is shaped by the political, social, and economic conditions of the state. In a setting where a rebel victory has completely overturned the incumbent regime and replaced its elites with a narrow group drawn from its own territory, the new governing authority's networks are likely to be tied primarily to those within the areas they previously controlled, especially when these constituents maintain ties that permeate across the country.

Moreover, where the ruling network possesses a relatively strong leader, the regime will tend toward personalism and the leader's consolidation of power (Svolik 2012, Geddes 2004). This should encourage opaqueness in decision-making and patrimonialism at the very top of the regime, which should trickle down from the ruling elite into the lower echelons of the regime's base. Emerging from this should be a broad set of individuals belonging to a relatively dense network that are tied to the regime and each other,³ and who are afforded greater access to the state.

What appears to be taking shape in Syria is the development of a privileged class that

does not map in any simple fashion onto economic strata, sect, piety, or ethnicity. Rather, while each of the above characteristics is salient to some extent, the fundamental feature of the rising social class is their connection to Idlib during the civil war. This group includes the people who are from (and stayed in) Idlib, as well as those who moved, forcibly or otherwise, to Idlib during the civil war. Many of these individuals, who certainly took on extraordinary costs, have begun to construct a narrative surrounding the revolution that centers their sacrifices and views those who remained in Asad regime-aligned territories skeptically. As such, in their view, they are an extension of the current ruling elite that produced victory over Asad, and they are the ones entitled to reap the rewards of its success.⁵

Contestation over ties to a revolutionary moment is not unique to Syria. Nevertheless, there are factors that may allow the social dynamics currently at play to produce a stable set of beneficiaries who form a privileged class in post-Asad Syria. First, there are clear historical social markers that allow individuals to differentiate class members from others. Second, those who resided in Idlib during HTS's stewardship of the Syrian Salvation Government were socialized into the norms associated with governance under HTS, providing them with an advantage in navigating state institutions during this transitional phase. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, they developed ties within the networks of

3 See El Amine and Mazur (2022) for a network-based understanding of meso-level groups.

4 In this piece, I draw on Bourdieu (1984, 114; 1985) when using the word class in a manner that extends beyond rigidly economic understandings of the term. Moreover, I emphasize the relevance of the social capital dimension perhaps to a greater extent than Bourdieu in *Distinction*, drawing on Hanna Batatu's (1979) reminder of the social networks that underly classes. It is also for this reason that I do not characterize this class as simply the state bourgeoisie (Waterbury 1991, Haddad 2012). While the burgeoning state bourgeoisie are a central feature of this class and are woven into the networks included within this privileged class, the class itself extends beyond them.

5 Of course, this does not imply that all those who resided in Idlib during the civil war carry this view.

the current ruling elite, providing them with better access to state resources than others. This further implies that they formed ties with one another, producing a network that is dense enough to potentially be a salient social grouping.

This superior social proximity to key decision-makers and others with access to decision-makers within the state not only confers upon them benefits, but also makes these individuals access points for many within the communities they are embedded in. When outside of Idlib, they become intermediaries who can decide who obtains access to influential individuals and who does not. Such individuals, particularly those with bureaucratic managerial positions, can play a role similar to that of the key (*miftah*) in the Asad regime, providing gateways to the resources of the state (Bishara 2013; Mazur 2021, 80). This positioning within Syria at a critical juncture, where the state and regime are being reshaped, could have long-term consequences on the social order.

To be clear, President Ahmed al-Sharaa's unifying statements have generally provided a broad umbrella, yet the behavior of the ruling elite since taking control of Syria has set the stage for reshaping the social order in this way. The relative power of al-Sharaa vis-à-vis his ruling network should lead to greater regime personalism (see Svulik 2012). Combined with the narrow construction of the ruling network and the general opaqueness of state management, these dynamics create conditions for a privileged class tied to the ruling elites. Even where the governing authority has attempted to resolve issues related to the opaqueness of procedures underlying recruitment, it has often centralized control over such procedures in a manner that may prevent recruitment from communities that

may be critical of actions taken by the state (see Karam Shaar Advisory Ltd. 2025A). More troubling is that the reach of the ruling elite appears to have spread quickly into the private sphere through their secretive management of the economic transition away from the business elites of the previous regime (Azhari 2025). This risks producing a crony capitalist system tied to the upper echelons of the ruling elite, similar to what emerged under Bashar al-Asad (see Haddad 2011).

These conditions are further amplified by the absence of clear ideological constraints in an atmosphere dominated by pragmatic logic. While many have worried about the Islamist or Salafist impulses of the new ruling elite, it has avoided firm ideological commitments, Islamic or otherwise, that might lead to institutionalized concessions to constituents. This has reassured some who feared the governing authority would move to impose strict religious restrictions through state institutions. Yet, the ruling elite's pragmatism has produced an opaque landscape in which the logic of survival takes precedence, potentially deepening and entrenching the privileged class as a support base that functions much like a sect or ethnic group.

Rather than delineating the boundaries of privileged access to state resources and elites through a strictly sectarian logic, which may not be feasible given the size of the sect, the most salient feature of the emerging privileged class is rooted in the social networks that developed during the civil war. This group is certainly Sunni in character, yet it excludes the vast majority of the Sunni population in Syria. While sectarian overtones may be invoked to suggest inclusion, particularly during periods of heightened sectarian tension, the fundamental structure taking

shape is more narrowly tied to a subset of Sunnis.⁶

What is outlined above is not a stable outcome but rather a trajectory I have observed with pessimism. Pressure to share power with elites drawn from other networks may lead to the building of institutions that diversify recruitment and access to the state's resources. Moreover, bottom-up pressure during this precarious period may also lead to the development of institutions that allay the concerns noted within this piece.

The actions taken by the governing authority in Syria could ultimately reshape this landscape before a relatively homogenous privileged class solidifies into a persistent feature of the social order. First, by diversifying and broadening the ruling elite with meaningful decision-making power, leaders can draw in other networks whose competing interests require the development of institutions. Second, the professionalization of bureaucracies across Syria in both recruitment and operations can help prevent the rise of such a privileged class. This requires that hiring be conducted according to clear procedures that promote merit-based practices, along with transparency in operations so that citizens can turn to state offices when needed, rather than relying on their social networks to reach a connected individual to address their concerns. The governing authority has announced several efforts aimed at the reform of the recruitment and training of state employees, yet such efforts have been piecemeal or have not yet been completely developed (Karam Shaar Advisory, Ltd. 2025B). Moreover, the initiatives proposed cannot completely resolve problems associated with shadow processes underlying access to the

state. Finally, the government's management of the economy should be done transparently, even when handling sensitive issues related to the businesses of Assad regime cronies. ♦

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⁶ This does not imply that sectarian divisions have not led to chauvinism or a callous disregard for the fears of non-Sunni communities among some.

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